

COMPETENCY-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL MODULE IN DRESSMAKING FOR LADIES SKIRT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13991804>

ABSTRACT

This research focused on the development and evaluation of the competency-based instructional module, which was developed based on the DepEd curriculum guidelines in dressmaking for ladies' skirts. TLE teachers and TESDA trainers experts evaluated the developed competency-based instructional module in terms of content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness. This descriptive study analyzes and evaluates data using a survey questionnaire, which was validated by experts in the field and tested for its consistency using Cronbach alpha. The mean was used to determine the evaluations of the TLE teachers and TESDA trainers experts, while the independent sample t-test was used to assess the significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed module. Both the TLE teachers and the TESDA trainers experts evaluated the "Competency-Based Instructional Module in Dressmaking for Ladies Skirt" as "Strongly Agree" relative to the content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness. There was no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the competency-based instructional module for making skirt garments in terms of content, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness. However, there was a significant difference in the evaluation of the TLE teachers and TESDA trainers experts in terms of format.

Keywords: *Dressmaking, Ladies Skirt, Competency-Based, Instructional Module*

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the key components of a nation's development. In a developing country like the Philippines, it plays a crucial role in eradicating poverty and upgrading the lives of every Filipino. It allows people to secure a job and the opportunity to earn decent compensation. But not just in employment, education could also help achieve personal and social life development by pursuing a person's interests and abilities. Hence, the government embarked on enhancing the education system by implementing Republic Act No. 10533, known as the Enhance K–12 Basic Education Program. Its goal is to create a functional basic education system that will produce productive and responsible citizens equipped with the essential competencies and skills for both life-long learning and employment. Under the K–12 programs, it focuses on the three main tracks, which are academic, arts and design, and technical-vocational.

Technical and vocational education helps people acquire practical skills and knowledge relating to occupations, which prepares them to work in a trade or as a technician. It is treated as a "ticket for the workplace." The aim of the technical-vocational track is to develop the skills and acquire the highest level of competency. Thus, the Tulong-Trabaho Act, also known as Republic No. 11230, was enacted to provide access to high-quality technical-vocational education and training to develop competencies, address job skill mismatches, and decrease unemployment in the Filipino workforce.

From the various technical skills under the technical-vocational track, one of the skills that demands labor in the industry is dressmaking. Dressmaking is a skill-oriented subject that has the potential to equip learners with skills that enable them to be self-employed, thus reducing the problem of employment in the country. Mendoza (2023) defined dressmaking as the art of making clothes, particularly women's clothing items such as skirts, blouses, and gowns. According to Ahmed (2023), dressmaking is a skill that can be learned by anyone who has an interest in and desire in making clothes.

Based on the curriculum of the Department of Education in Grade 10 dressmaking, the learners are expected to produce ladies' skirts, blouses, and trousers across the four quarters of the school year. After finishing the course, graduates can take a competency assessment that will assess their skills, knowledge, attitude, and work values based on training regulations (TRs) promulgated by the Technical Education Skills Development Authority (TESDA) Board. Students who pass the assessment procedure will obtain a National Certificate, or NC, at their respective levels, which becomes one of their valuable qualifications for landing a job. However, many factors affect the teaching and learning of dressmaking. One factor is the availability and usability of instructional materials such as textbooks, modules, worksheets, and teaching guides.

Vice President and former Education Secretary Sara Duterte has stated that the "most pressing issue" facing the Philippine education sector is the lack of resources and facilities for schools (Inquirer, 2023). The Alliance of Concerned Teachers (as cited in Mateo, 2019) revealed that there is a lack of printed learning materials, including technical vocational livelihood courses, in public schools. Tolentino (as cited in Baron, 2023) also

said there is a shortage of learning materials, which manifests educational challenges. These learning materials and resources include learning modules and other media such as audio, video, and animations.

This is also true in the study of Basal (2022), entitled “Instructional Competencies of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Teachers: Basis for a Competency-Based Module,” whose findings revealed that there were problems met by the TLE teachers, such as inadequate instructional materials in the classroom. Moreover, the study of Barrera (2022), entitled “Availability of Instructional Materials Model of the Technical-Vocational Livelihood Curriculum Implementation for Public Senior High Schools,” signifies that there is insufficient instructional availability among senior high schools offering TVL strand, and teacher-trainers use every resource and assume accountability for the improvement of instruction. The lack of these instructional materials could develop a learning crisis among the students that must be addressed to support learning.

According to Barrera, instructional materials are the primary need for all students to develop their skills and carry out all the activities in the classroom successfully. Lane (2022) also states that instructional materials are important as they provide structure for engaging the students to learn different concepts and master skills. In addition, Lane emphasizes that the teacher must utilize various instructional materials, such as textbooks, workbooks, manuals, modules, and presentations, to teach efficiently. Furthermore, NMSI (2023) cited that quality instructional materials such as textbooks, digital resources, and other educational tools provide learning resources and offer the framework for assessment.

Jimenez (2020), on the other hand, suggests that teachers should have the courage and patience to continuously develop instructional material that will help every learner master different competency. The ALS-EST Program (2019) also suggests that technical-vocational teachers should create supplementary learning materials to meet the needs of the students. As emphasized, these learning materials should integrate competency-based learning to ensure mastery of the skills. A competency-based approach to teaching and learning relies on the importance of mastery of specific skills and competencies rather than mere completion of a subject. Practical hands-on activities are integrated as well into the learning process for a much more meaningful learning experience.

Hence, the researcher of this study is driven to develop instructional modules that are competency-based to support learning, address learning gaps, cultivate interests, and develop the skills of the learners in dressmaking. The researcher believes that this lack of learning and instructional materials must be immediately resolved to prevent learning difficulties and crises faced by the learners and the teachers as well. Developing a competency-based instructional module is necessary and highly relevant, as it will focus on achieving competencies required in the industry. This will equip learners with the essential skills and knowledge to succeed and become experts in the craft. Mastery of specific skills and competencies can be attained, and learners will be well-prepared to meet the challenges of the industry.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop and evaluate a competency-based instructional module in dressmaking for ladies' skirts. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What competency-based activities during the first quarter lessons were developed into an instructional module in making ladies skirt garments based on the DepEd curriculum guide?
2. What was the evaluation of the TLE teachers and the TESDA trainers on the developed instructional module in making skirt garments based on the following criteria:
 - a. content
 - b. format
 - c. presentation and organization
 - d. accuracy
 - e. usefulness
3. Was there a significant difference between the evaluation of the TLE teachers and the TESDA trainers based on the criteria?
4. What were the comments and suggestions of the respondents to further improve the developed material?

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of a descriptive method of research as it gathers, describes, analyzes, and evaluates data using a survey questionnaire, which was validated by experts in the field. A reliability test was also conducted to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the survey questions using Cronbach alpha with a 0.97 reliability coefficient. The researcher used purposive sampling in selecting the respondents to the study. A total of 30 respondents, composed of twenty (20) TLE teachers and ten (10) experts who were TESDA trainers, evaluated the developed competency-based instructional module in terms of content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness. The mean was used to determine the evaluations of the TLE teachers and TESDA trainers experts, while the independent sample t-test was used to assess the significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the competency-based instructional module. The data gathering instrument used in this study was the survey questionnaire checklist, which was adapted and modified based on DepEd's Guidelines and Processes for Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) Assessment and Evaluation for print resources. It was validated by experts composed of dressmaking teachers, masters' teachers, a language teacher, and a school research focal person. A reliability test was then conducted to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the survey questions using Cronbach alpha. A

reliability coefficient of 0.97 was obtained, which proves the internal consistency of the instrument.

The scale with an adjectival equivalent was used as follows:

Numerical Value	Scale	Descriptive Interpretation
4	3:25– 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree (A)
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree (D)
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the summary of the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the “Competency-Based Instructional Module in Dressmaking for Ladies Skirt” as regards to its content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness.

Table 1

Summary of the Respondents’ Evaluations on the Competency-Based Instructional Module in Dressmaking for Ladies Skirt

Criteria	Respondents			
	TLE Teachers		TESDA Trainers	
	AM	VI	AM	VI
1. Content	3.95	SA	3.78	SA
2. Format	3.96	SA	3.64	SA
3. Presentation and Organization	3.92	SA	3.70	SA
4. Accuracy	3.85	SA	3.56	SA
5. Usefulness	3.89	SA	3.74	SA
Average Mean	3.91	SA	3.68	SA
Overall Average Mean	3.80 – Strongly Agree			

As indicated in Table 1, both groups of respondents strongly agree on the competency-based instructional module in making skirt garments in terms of its content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness, with an average mean of 3.91 and 3.68, respectively, and an overall average mean of 3.80.

Table 2 presents the summary of the test of the significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the “Competency-Based Instructional Module in Dressmaking for Ladies Skirt” as regards to its content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness.

Table 2

Summary of Test of the Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Competency-Based Instructional Module in Dressmaking for Ladies Skirt

Criteria	TLE Teachers		TESDA Trainers		Computed t value	Decision	Interpretation
	OAM	S	OAM	s			
a. Content	3.95	0.10	3.78	0.14	1.40	Fail to reject the H _o	Not significant
b. Format	3.96	0.02	3.64	0.17	2.41	Reject the H _o	Significant
c. Presentation and Organization	3.92	0.06	3.70	0.13	1.77	Fail to reject the H _o	Not significant
d. Accuracy	3.85	0.11	3.56	0.21	1.78	Fail to reject the H _o	Not significant
e. Usefulness	3.89	0.08	3.74	0.19	0.99	Fail to reject the H _o	Not significant

As reflected in Table 2, the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the competency-based instructional module in making skirt garments does not show significant differences on its content, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness, as shown in the respective computed t values. However, as to the format of the module, there is a significant difference in the evaluations of the TLE teachers and TESDA trainers.

DISCUSSION

The above findings signify that TLE teachers and TESDA trainers completely approved the content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness of the competency-based instructional module in dressmaking for ladies’ skirts. Hence, the instructional module is highly acceptable and useful for its target users.

Conclusions

With the results and findings of this study, the researcher came up with the following conclusions:

1. The developed “Competency-Based Instructional Module in Dressmaking for Ladies Skirt” had reached the expectations of the TLE teachers and TESDA trainers experts in the quality of learning materials in terms of content, format, presentation and organization, accuracy, and usefulness.
2. There were some comments and suggestions offered by the TLE teachers and TESDA trainers to further improve the competency-based instructional module in making skirt garments.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn in this study, the researcher hereby recommends the following:

1. Students and teachers may use the “Competency-Based Instructional Module in Dressmaking for Ladies Skirt” to assess its effectiveness.
 2. The developed competency-based instructional module may be validated by experts from the Department of Education for further improvements and for uploading to DepEd’s learning portal.
 3. The school administrators may conduct training for teachers on how to develop competency-based instructional modules.
 4. Teachers of dressmaking are encouraged to develop competency-based instructional modules in other areas of dressmaking that students can use for individual or advanced study.
 5. School administrators may produce copies of the competency-based instructional module readily available in the library hub of the school and for distance learning.
 6. Parents are encouraged to use the competency-based instructional module at home for collaborative learning with their child.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher followed a systematic way of gathering data, which involves selecting potential and suitable respondents for the study. The researcher contacted and discussed the purpose of the study as well as its relevance and significance to the target respondents, seeking their permission to evaluate the developed competency-based instructional module. The researchers also informed the target respondents of the procedures, which emphasize data privacy. Respondents were informed that their personal information would be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Moreover, they were

not manipulated, threatened, or forced to participate in the study. But rather, their rights to withdraw at any time from the survey were opened and considered.

The module was evaluated by the TLE dressmaking teachers coming from different schools and TESDA dressmaking trainers using a validated survey questionnaire to check if the developed instructional module is useful and applicable for use. A total of 30 respondents, of which 10 are TESDA trainers and 20 are TLE teachers, answered the survey questionnaire administered through Google Forms or in printed form. After gathering the data, the researcher tallied, analyzed, and interpreted the results solely based on what the respondents had answered. The data were not manipulated or falsified to favor the desired results. Rather, it was statistically treated to get actual results.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her sincerest gratitude and appreciation to the profound people who have greatly helped, motivated, and inspired her to accomplish and succeed in this endeavor—to her adviser, members of the panel, validators, TLE teachers and TESDA trainers, her respondents, for sharing their time and expertise to make this study a successful one, and to her family for all the love, support, and understanding.

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